

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Women entrepreneurship performance with special reference to Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

Entrepreneurs play a key role in economic activity. They have skills and good new ideas to market and make the right decisions to make the idea. In this dynamic world, women entrepreneurs are a significant part of the global expedition for sustained economic development and social progress. Due to the growing industrialization, urbanization, social legislation and along with the spread of higher education and awareness, the emergence of Women owned businesses are highly increasing in the economies of almost all countries. The increasing presence of women in the business field as entrepreneurs has changed the demographic characteristics of business and economic growth of the country. Women entrepreneurs faces many genders related challenges they face in the competitive business world with their male counterparts. Even, women enterprises are playing a more active role in the society and in the economy. This study focused on the role and contribution of women entrepreneurs, women entrepreneur's capability and performance, government initiatives and promotions and problems faced by urban and rural women entrepreneurs and suggestions for future prospects for development of women entrepreneurs, especially in the district of Visakhapatnam.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurship; Economic growth; Women empowerment; Urban and Rural entrepreneurship; Entrepreneur's capabilities

1. Introduction

The increasing presence of women in the business field as entrepreneurs over the past two decades has changed the demographic characteristics of business and overall economic growth in the country. However, the entrepreneurial world in India is still dominated by men. Female entrepreneurs are concentrated in the areas of small-scale entrepreneurship characterized by limited growth and tend to be home-based. Their role in the large scale and technology-based industries is still quite limited. Many research studies point out that one of the major factors restricting the growth of women enterprises in India is lack of finance. Women often have fewer opportunities than men to gain access to credit for various reasons including lack of collateral, an unwillingness to accept household assets as collateral and negative perceptions of women entrepreneurs by loan officers in the absence of credit ratings and a proper business plan. A general lack of experience and exposure, heavy paperwork and high transaction cost associated with accessing credit also restricts women from venturing out and dealing with banking institutions. As a result, they usually depend on the family members or informal sources for their capital requirements which restricts the growth and survival of their enterprises.

1.1. Concept of Women Entrepreneurship

The history of economic development of all countries whether developing or developed, has evidenced the fact that entrepreneurs have made a significant contribution in this respect. Entrepreneurship among women can be seen as a tool for Employment and Income generation. Efforts are been made by various government and non-government

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agencies all over the world to promote women entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship is a vital need of a developing nation. According to George Bernard shaw, “The people who get on in this world are the people who get up and look for the circumstances they want, and, if they can’t find them, they create them”. Virtually everyone is an entrepreneur in some part of their lives. Anyone who exhibits the characteristics of self-employment, creativity, self-decision making and risk taking attitude can be rightly called as person with entrepreneurial traits. When these traits are exhibited by a person in running a business is known as entrepreneur.

1.2. Importance of the study

The study on women empowerment through entrepreneurship have been taken up to add value to what other researcher have discussed, so that it becomes favorable for women to become entrepreneur. To inspire women so that the social taboos are removed and they can make themselves financially independent. Men should encourage their spouse to become independent and a single women should no longer be dependent on people to help her financially. Gender gap should be narrowed to increase the income of the country.

2. Literature review

A brief review of literature pertaining to entrepreneurship has been presented below. The secondary source of data included are articles, journals, thesis, newspapers, conference papers and websites. Therefore, the reviewing past related studies is as important as the present study. All these studies directly or indirectly are deeply connected to the present title of research.

2.1. Women Entrepreneurs in Rural Visakhapatnam

- Balaji Veju (2018), The policies and promotions of government have encouraged women owned enterprise which led towards the increase in the percentage share of women investment in MSME's from 11.9 percent during the year 1940- 50 to 25.7 percent during the year 2006- 16 in Andhra Pradesh.
- Dr C Viswanatha Reddy and Shree Vidyanikethan (2012), another research study conducted on identify the problems and prospects of the respondents in Chittoor district of Andhra Pradesh revealed that Women entrepreneurs from joint family faced many problems but the support and help by the government motivated women to venture in business.
- B. Sambasiva Roa (2009), Self-help groups (SHG'S) have helped the people to make their living standard better at a considerable level and help women to attain economic sustainability.

2.2. Research questions

Hence, the study aiming to bring out the following queries

- What is the socio-economic status of women entrepreneurs in the district of Visakhapatnam?
- What is the impact of government promotion and schemes on women empowerment?
- How do you differentiate performance between rural and urban entrepreneurs?

2.3. Statement of problem

The available literature on women entrepreneurship does not provide in-depth knowledge about certain factors, which are influenced to promote the women empowerment in business. Women entrepreneurs have not been able to achieve their full potential in a male dominated business society due to the innumerable constraints they face in their endeavor to set up viable business ventures. The study is designed to examine these unknown factors of women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam. This study hoped that the results of this research will reveal the obstacles to the growth of businesses owned by women so as to attract national attention to help alleviate the problems.

Objectives of the study

- To review the socio-economic status of women entrepreneurs in the region of Visakhapatnam.
- To analyzes the factors that influences the women entrepreneur's performance in between rural urban regions in Visakhapatnam.

Hypotheses of the study

- H1: There is a positive impact of socio-economic status of women entrepreneurship between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam.

- H2: There is a difference of the women entrepreneur's performance between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam.
- H2: There is a difference of the women entrepreneur's business capabilities between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam.

3. Methodology

The design of the present pilot study is descriptive and analytical in nature. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfill our objectives has been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data is collected from the women entrepreneurs, who are residing in both urban and rural areas of Visakhapatnam through interviews and discussions regarding different aspects of the women entrepreneur's empowerment and performance. The study, it has been taken 50 as sample for this study and taken equal proportion of sample 25 each for both urban and rural entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region for this analysis.

The study is also based on the secondary data consisting of entrepreneurship and empowerment related articles, research papers, various text books, government schemes and consent web sites are also used to supplement the secondary data.

This pilot study purpose 50 sample entrepreneurs have collected data with simple and random sampling.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as statistical descriptions, correlation, regression, chi-square test is used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS software.

Scope and limitation

The below mentioned are the constraints, which are carried out for this pilot study

- The collection of data analysis is restricted to both urban and rural areas of Visakhapatnam region only.
- The study is limited by time constraints.
- The accuracy of study based on the primary data depends upon the reliability of information provided by the respondents. Hence, to that extent the study suffers the limitation of generalization of the findings.

3.1. Data analysis

This wholly study has been classified in five parts:

- Review the women entrepreneur's socio-economic demographic profile.
- Analysis of Women Entrepreneur's Business capabilities.
- Analysis of Women Entrepreneurship performance on woman empowerment of Urban and Rural Regions.

4. Results of women entrepreneurs Socio-Economic Demographic Profile

This part of study focuses on demographic profile of the women entrepreneurs. The study the demographic factors and their influence the women entrepreneur's business capabilities and performance. Demographic characteristics are easy to identify. These include qualities such as age, educational qualifications, monthly income and social status; hence the relevant data is collected and evaluated.

An attempt is made to analyze four socio-economic demographic factors, which are presented, here under Table-1 to Table-4.

The above Table-1 presents the percentage distribution of socio-economic characteristics of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Age classification is one of the parameter, which influences the strength of this study. Out of total sample 50; age is as follows, below 20 years 3(6 percent), 21 to 30 years 10(20 percent), 31 to 40 years 15 (30 percent), 41 to 50 years 14 (28 percent), 51 to 60 years 5 (10%) and above 60 years 4 (8 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; below 20 years 2(8 percent), 21 to 30 years 4 (16 percent), 31 to 40 years 7 (28 percent), 41 to 50 years 9 (36 percent), 51 to 60 years 2(8 percent) and above 60 years 1 (4 percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; below 20 years 1(4 percent), 21 to 30 years 5 (20 percent),

31 to 40 years 8 (32 percent), 41 to 50 years 5 (20 percent), 51 to 60 years 3(12 percent) and above 60 years 3 (12 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is seen high and positive correlation (0.94) and relationship strength is 88.36 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen high positive correlation (0.91) and relationship strength 82.81 percent. These results statistically significant.

Table 1 Age Group of Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
< 20 Years	2	1	3
	(8)	(4)	(6)
21-30 Years	4	5	10
	(16)	(10)	(20)
31-40 Years	7	8	15
	(28)	(32)	(30)
41-50 Years	9	5	14
	(36)	(20)	(28)
51-60 Years	2	3	5
	(8)	(12)	(10)
>60 Years	1	3	4
	(4)	(12)	(8)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.94 (0.005)	0.91 (0.00117)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table 2 Education Qualifications of Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Illiterate	0	3	3
	(0)	(12)	(6)
Primary Education	2	5	7
	(8)	(20)	(14)
Secondary Education	6	3	9
	(24)	(12)	(18)
Intermediate	6	8	14
	(24)	(32)	(28)
Graduate	9	5	14
	(36)	(20)	(28)
Post Graduate	2	1	3
	(8)	(4)	(6)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.90 (0.1455)	0.80 (0.0560)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-2 presents the percentage distribution of socio-economic characteristics of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Educational Qualifications is the parameter, which influences the strength of this study. Out of total sample 50; educational qualifications are as follows, illiterate 3(6 percent), primary Education 7 (14 percent), secondary education 9 (18 percent), intermediate education 14 (28 percent), graduate 14 (28%) and post graduate 3 (6 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; illiterate (nil), primary education 2 (8 percent), secondary education 6 (24 percent), intermediate education 6 (24 percent), graduate 9(36 percent) and postgraduate 2 (8 percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; illiterate 3(12 percent), primary education 5 (20 percent), secondary education 3 (12 percent), intermediate education 8 (32 percent), graduate 5(20 percent) and post graduate 1 (4 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed high and positive correlation (0.90) and relationship strength is 81 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen high positive correlation (0.80) and relationship strength 64 percent. These results statistically insignificant.

Table 3 Monthly Income of Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Less than Rs. 20,000	2	8	10
	(8)	(32)	(10)
Rs. 20,001-30,000	6	7	13
	(24)	(28)	(26)
Rs. 30,001-40,000	8	4	12
	(32)	(16)	(24)
Rs. 40,001-50,000	5	3	8
	(20)	(12)	(16)
Above Rs. 50,000	4	3	7
	(16)	(12)	(14)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.53 (0.3580)	0.58 (0.3050)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-3 presents the percentage distribution of socio-economic characteristics of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Monthly income of women entrepreneurs is one of the parameter, which influences the strength of this study. Out of total sample 50; monthly is as follows, less than Rs. 20,000 10(20 percent), Rs. 20,001-30,000 13 (26 percent), Rs. 30,001-40,000 12 (24 percent), Rs. 40,001-50,000 8 (16 percent) and Rs. 30,001-40,000 7 (14 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; less than Rs. 20,000 2 (8 percent), Rs. 20,001-30,000 6 (24 percent), Rs. 30,001-40,000 8 (32 percent), Rs. 40,001-50,000 5 (20 percent) and Rs. 30,001-40,000 4 (816 percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; less than Rs. 20,000 8 (32 percent), Rs. 20,001-30,000 7 (28 percent), Rs. 30,001-40,000 4 (16 percent), Rs. 40,001-50,000 3 (12 percent) and Rs. 30,001-40,000 3 (12 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is seen positive correlation (0.53) and relationship strength is 28.09 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen medium positive correlation (0.58) and relationship strength 33.64 percent. These results statistically significant.

Table 4 Social Status of Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Forward Caste	10	9	19
	(40)	(36)	(38)
Other backward Caste	6	9	15
	(24)	(36)	(30)
SC	2	3	5
	(8)	(12)	(10)
ST	2	2	4
	(8)	(8)	(8)
Minority	5	2	7
	(20)	(8)	(14)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.94 (0.0175)	0.95 (0.0133)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-4 presents the percentage distribution of socio-economic characteristics of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Social status is the parameter, which influences the strength of this study. Out of total sample 50; Social status are as follows, Forward caste 19 (38 percent), other backward caste 15 (30 percent), Scheduled caste 5 (10 percent), Scheduled tribes 4 (8 percent), and Minorities 7 (14 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; Forward caste 10 (40 percent), other backward caste 6 (24 percent), Scheduled caste 2 (8 percent), Scheduled tribes 2 (8 percent), and Minorities 5 (20 percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; Forward caste 9 (36 percent), other backward caste 9 (36 percent), Scheduled caste 3 (12 percent), Scheduled tribes 2 (8 percent), and Minorities 2 (8 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that high and positive correlation (0.94) and relationship strength is 88.66 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen high positive correlation (0.95) and relationship strength 90.25 percent. These results statistically significant.

5. Discussion of Women Entrepreneur's Business capabilities and empowerment

An attempt is made analyzes the Women Entrepreneur's Business capabilities and empowerment. There are four major factors considered to measures the business capability of women entrepreneurs and their empowerment. Selected factors of women entrepreneur's business capabilities are

- Positive attitude
- Confidence level
- Risk taking ability
- Problem-solving ability.

These factors are analyzed and presented, here under Table-5 to Table-8.

Table 5 Positive Attitude of Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Very Good	12	8	20
	(48)	(32)	(40)
Good	7	8	15
	(28)	(32)	(30)
Average	5	6	11
	(20)	(24)	(22)
Poor	1	3	4
	(4)	(12)	(8)
Very Poor	0	0	0
	(0)	(0)	(0)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.98 (0.0034)	0.96 (0.0095)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table 6 Confidence Level of Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Very Good	13	10	23
	(64)	(40)	(46)
Good	7	7	14
	(28)	(28)	(28)
Average	5	6	11
	(20)	(24)	(22)
Poor	0	1	1
	(0)	(4)	(2)
Very Poor	0	1	1
	(0)	(4)	(2)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.10 (0.8728)	0.10 (0.9546)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-5 presents the percentage distribution of women entrepreneur's business capabilities of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Positive attitude is one of factor, which influences to measure the women entrepreneur's business competence for their empowerment. Out of total sample 50; Positive attitude is as follows, very good 20 (40 percent), Good 15 (30 percent), Average 11 (22 percent), Poor 4 (8 percent), and very poor 0 (no percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; Very good 12 (24 percent), Good 7 (28 percent), Average 5 (20 percent), Poor 1 (4 percent), and very poor 0 (no percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; Very good 8 (32 percent), Good 8 (32 percent), Average 6 (24 percent), Poor 3 (12 percent), and very poor 0 (no percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that high and positive correlation (0.98) and relationship strength is 96.04 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen high positive correlation (0.96) and relationship strength 92.16 percent. These results statistically significant.

The above Table-6 presents the percentage distribution of women entrepreneur’s business capabilities of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Confidence level is one of factor, which influences to measure the women entrepreneur’s business competence for their empowerment. Out of total sample 50; Confidence level is as follows, very good 23 (46 percent), Good 14 (28 percent), Average 11 (22 percent), Poor 1 (two percent), and very poor 1 (two percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; Very good 13 (52 percent), Good 7 (28 percent), Average 5 (20 percent), Poor 0 (no percent), and very poor 0 (no percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; Very good 10 (40 percent), Good 7 (28 percent), Average 6 (24 percent), Poor 1 (two percent), and very poor 1 (two percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that very low positive correlation (0.10) and relationship strength is one percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen high positive correlation (0.10) and relationship strength one percent. These results statistically insignificant.

Table 7 Risk Taking Ability of Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Very Good	9	6	15
	(36)	(24)	(30)
Good	11	9	20
	(44)	(36)	(40)
Average	3	5	8
	(12)	(20)	(16)
Poor	1	3	4
	(4)	(12)	(8)
Very Poor	1	2	3
	(4)	(4)	(6)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.10 (0.8728)	0.11 (0.8729)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-7 presents the percentage distribution of women entrepreneur’s business capabilities of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Risk Taking Ability is one of factor, which influences to measure the women entrepreneur’s business competence for their empowerment. Out of total sample 50; Risk taking ability is as follows, very good 15 (30 percent), Good 20 (40 percent), Average 8 (16 percent), Poor 4 (8 percent), and very poor 3 (6 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; Very good 9 (36 percent), Good 11 (44 percent), Average 3 (12 percent), Poor 1 (4 percent), and very poor 1 (4 percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; Very good 6 (24 percent), Good 9 (36 percent), Average 5 (20 percent), Poor 3 (12 percent), and very poor 2 (8 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that very low positive correlation (0.10) and relationship strength is one percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen high positive correlation (0.11) and relationship strength 1.1 percent. These results statistically insignificant.

Table 8 Problem Solving Ability

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Very Good	12	9	21
	(48)	(36)	(42)
Good	9	7	16
	(36)	(28)	(32)
Average	3	5	8
	(12)	(20)	(16)
Poor	1	2	3
	(4)	(8)	(6)
Very Poor	0	2	2
	(0)	(8)	(4)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.10 (0.8726)	0.99 (0.0621)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-8 shows the percentage distribution of women entrepreneur's business capabilities of urban and rural women entrepreneurs in Visakhapatnam region. Problem Solving Ability is one of factor, which influences to measure the women entrepreneur's business competence for their empowerment. Out of total sample 50; Problem solving ability is as follows, very good 21 (42 percent), Good 20 (40 percent), Average 8 (16 percent), Poor 3 (6 percent), and very poor 2 (4 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; Very good 12 (48 percent), Good 9 (36 percent), Average 3 (12 percent), Poor 1 (4 percent), and very poor 0 (no percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; Very good 9 (36 percent), Good 7 (28 percent), Average 5 (20 percent), Poor 2 (8 percent), and very poor 2 (8 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that very low positive correlation (0.10) and relationship strength is one percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen high positive correlation (0.99) and relationship strength 99 percent. These results statistically insignificant.

6. Discussion of impact of Women Entrepreneurship Performance on woman empowerment of Urban and Rural Regions

This part of pilot study discusses and analyzes the impact of women entrepreneurship on woman empowerment of Urban and Rural Regions. There are four major factors considered from main study to differentiate the women entrepreneurship performance between urban and rural entrepreneurs. Selected factors of women entrepreneur's business performance measures are

- business performance
- business challenges
- business opportunities
- Business success.

These factors are analyzed and presented, here under Table-8 to Table-12.

Table 9 Women entrepreneurship on woman empowerment of urban and rural

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Strongly Agree	10	10	20
	(40)	(40)	(40)
Partially Agree	5	6	11
	(20)	(24)	(44)
Agree	4	5	9
	(16)	(20)	(18)
Disagree	4	2	6
	(16)	(8)	(12)
Strongly Disagree	2	2	4
	(8)	(8)	(8)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.98 (0.0034)	0.99 (0.0012)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

Table 10 Rural Women Entrepreneurs faces more challenges than Urban Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Strongly Agree	11	9	20
	(44)	(36)	(40)
Partially Agree	9	7	16
	(36)	(28)	(32)
Agree	4	4	8
	(16)	(16)	(16)
Disagree	1	4	5
	(4)	(16)	(10)
Strongly Disagree	0	1	1
	(0)	(4)	(2)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.10 (0.8729)	0.98 (0.0034)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-9 shows the percentage distribution of women entrepreneurship on woman empowerment of urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam region. Business Performance factor, which is measured the women entrepreneurship on empowerment impact between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam. Out of total sample 50; Business performance is as follows, strongly agree 20 (40 percent), partially agree 11 (22 percent), agree 9 (18 percent), disagree 6 (12 percent), and strongly disagree 4 (8 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 10 (40 percent), partially agree 6 (24 percent), agree 5 (20 percent), disagree 4 (16 percent), and strongly disagree 2 (8 percent). Whereas, Rural

Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 10 (40 percent), partially agree 6 (24 percent), agree 5 (20 percent), disagree 2 (8 percent), and strongly disagree 2 (8 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that very high positive correlation (0.98) and relationship strength is 96.04 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen very high positive correlation (0.99) and relationship strength 99 percent. These results statistically significant.

The above Table-10 shows the percentage distribution of women entrepreneurship on woman empowerment of urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam region. Business Challenges, which is measured the women entrepreneurship on empowerment impact between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam. Out of total sample 50; Business challenges is as follows, strongly agree 20 (40 percent), partially agree 16 (32 percent), agree 8 (16 percent), disagree 5 (10 percent), and strongly disagree 1 (2 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 11 (44 percent), partially agree 9 (36 percent), agree 4 (16 percent), disagree 1 (4 percent), and strongly disagree 0 (no percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 9 (36 percent), partially agree 7 (28 percent), agree 4 (16 percent), disagree 4 (16 percent), and strongly disagree 2 (8 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that very low positive correlation (0.10) and relationship strength is one percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen very high positive correlation (0.98) and relationship strength 96 percent. These results statistically insignificant for urban area significant rural areas.

Table 11 Urban Women Entrepreneurs are more opportunities than Rural Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Strongly Agree	10	8	18
	(40)	(32)	(36)
Partially Agree	7	9	16
	(28)	(36)	(32)
Agree	4	6	10
	(16)	(24)	(20)
Disagree	3	2	5
	(12)	(8)	(10)
Strongly Disagree	1	0	1
	(4)	(0)	(2)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.96 (0.0095)	0.97 (0.0062)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-11 shows the percentage distribution of women entrepreneurship on woman empowerment of urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam region. Business opportunities factor, which is measured the women entrepreneurship on empowerment impact between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam. Out of total sample 50; Business opportunities is as follows, strongly agree 18 (36 percent), partially agree 16 (32 percent), agree 10 (20 percent), disagree 5 (10 percent), and strongly disagree 1 (2 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 10 (40 percent), partially agree 7 (28 percent), agree 4 (16 percent), disagree 3 (12 percent), and strongly disagree 1 (4 percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 8 (32 percent), partially agree 9 (36 percent), agree 6 (24 percent), disagree 2 (8 percent), and strongly disagree 0 (no percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that very high positive correlation (0.96) and relationship strength is 92.16 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen very high positive correlation (0.97) and relationship strength 94.09 percent. These results statistically significant.

Table 12 Urban Women Entrepreneurs have more success in business than Rural Women Entrepreneurs

Description	Urban Entrepreneurs	Rural Entrepreneurs	Total Entrepreneurs
Strongly Agree	10	6	16
	(40)	(24)	(32)
Partially Agree	11	7	18
	(44)	(28)	(36)
Agree	3	6	9
	(12)	(24)	(18)
Disagree	1	4	5
	(4)	(16)	(10)
Strongly Disagree	0	2	2
	(0)	(4)	(4)
Total	25	25	50
	(100)	(100)	(100)
*Correlation (P-Value)	0.99 (0.0012)	0.91 (0.032)	-

Source: Primary Data; * Computed Values The values in brackets indicate that Percentage of Response

The above Table-12 shows the percentage distribution of women entrepreneurship on woman empowerment of urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam region. Business Success factor, which is measured the women entrepreneurship on empowerment impact between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam. Out of total sample 50; Business success is as follows, strongly agree 16 (32 percent), partially agree 18 (36 percent), agree 9 (18 percent), disagree 5 (10 percent), and strongly disagree 2 (4 percent).

It can be seen from region wise sample; Urban Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 10 (40 percent), partially agree 11 (44 percent), agree 3 (12 percent), disagree 1 (4 percent), and strongly disagree 0 (no percent). Whereas, Rural Region out of 25 sample; strongly agree 6 (24 percent), partially agree 7 (28 percent), agree 6 (24 percent), disagree 4 (16 percent), and strongly disagree 2 (8 percent).

For correlation; total to urban region is observed that very high positive correlation (0.99) and relationship strength is 98.01 percent. On other hand, total to rural region is also seen very high positive correlation (0.91) and relationship strength 82.81 percent. These results statistically significant.

6.1. Chi-Square Analysis for Study

This chi-square measures to compare a collection of definite data with some hypothetical expected distribution. It is a statistical test commonly used to compare observed data with data we would expect to obtain according to a specific hypothesis. The chi-square test is testing the null hypothesis, which explained that there is no difference between the expected and observed result. This point of study is to find the positive impact of demographic profile on entrepreneurship on women empowerment in Visakhapatnam is taken four sub-hypotheses, which are tested by using chi-square test by considered demographic variables and other variables:

The formula for calculating chi-square = $(O - E)^2 / E$

6.2. Testing of Hypothesis for Study (Entrepreneurship on women empowerment and Its Variables)

- H1: There is a positive impact of socio-economic status of entrepreneurship on women empowerment between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam.

Table 13 Testing of hypotheses with Demographics on Entrepreneurship on Women Empowerment

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS					
Variables	Sub Hypothesis	Chi-Square	Critical Table	Hypothesis Result	Significance
Age (S1)	Age Group is positive impact on women entrepreneurship between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam	2.85	11.07	Accepted	0.7224
Education Qualification (S2)	Education Qualification is positive impact on women entrepreneurship between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam.	6.58	11.07	Accepted	0.2538
Monthly Earnings (S3)	Monthly income earnings are positive impact on women entrepreneurship between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam	5.65	9.49	Accepted	0.2265
Social Status (S4)	Social Status is positive impact on women entrepreneurship between rural and urban regions in Visakhapatnam.	2.13	9.49	Accepted	0.7103

Source: Computed; * Significant at 5% level, the result is not significant at $p < 0.05$

6.2.1. Inference

It can be seen from the above table shows the chi-square values of given first hypothesis of study has four sub hypotheses relating to personnel profiles of entrepreneurs on women empowerment. By applied Chiquare test, it is indicated that all four demographic variables are positively impact on the women entrepreneurs both urban and rural areas of Visakhapatnam region. Where, calculated Chi-square values of the four variables below the critical value, hence all these sub-hypotheses are accepted at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is found that age, education qualifications, earnings capacity and social status are personnel profiles of respondents, these are subjective factors for decide the performance of entrepreneurs on women empowerment between urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam.

- H2: There is a difference of the women entrepreneur's capabilities of business success between rural urban regions in Visakhapatnam.

Table 14 Testing of hypotheses with Women Entrepreneurs Business Capabilities

CHI-SQUARE ANALYS				
Variables	Sub Hypothesis	Chi-Square	Hypothesis Result	Significance
Positive Attitude (S1)	Positive Attitude is different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs	1.96	Accepted	0.7435
Confidence Level (S2)	Confidence Level is different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs	1.50	Accepted	0.8262
Risk Taking Ability (S3)	Risk Taking Ability is different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs	2.63	Accepted	0.6209
Problem Solving Ability (S4)	Problem Solving Ability is different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs.	1.66	Accepted	0.7962

Source: Computed; * Significant at 5% level, the result is not significant at $p < 0.05$; **Critical Value $F_{\alpha 0.05, (4)}$ is 9.49

6.2.2. Inference

It can be seen from the above table No-14, shows the chi-square values of given second hypothesis of study has four sub hypotheses relating to women entrepreneur's business capabilities. Which includes positive attitude, confidence level, risk taking ability and problem-solving ability.

By applied Chiquare test, it is indicated that all four sub-hypotheses of entrepreneur's business capabilities as variables are tested to find the difference of the women entrepreneur's capabilities of business success between rural urban regions in Visakhapatnam. Where, calculated Chi-square values of the four variables below the critical value, hence all these sub-hypotheses are accepted at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is found that positive attitude, confidence level, risk taking ability and problem-solving ability are entrepreneur's business capabilities, and these are subjective factors differentiating the performance of women entrepreneurs between urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam. Further, it concluded that as per pilot study revealed that women entrepreneur's business capabilities and success is different between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam.

- H3: There is a difference of the women entrepreneur's performance between rural urban regions in Visakhapatnam.

Table 15 Testing of hypotheses with Women Entrepreneur's Business Performance between urban rural areas of Visakhapatnam

CHI-SQUARE ANALYS				
Variables	Sub Hypothesis	Chi-Square	Hypothesis Result	Significance
Business Performance (S1)	Business performance is different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs	1.96	Accepted	0.7435
Business Challenges (S2)	Business Challenges are different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs	2.23	Accepted	0.6933
Business Opportunities (S3)	Business Opportunities are different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs	10.05	Rejected	0.9016
Business Success (S4)	Business Success is different between rural and urban Entrepreneurs.	4.62	Accepted	0.3289

Source: Computed; * Significant at 5% level, the result is not significant at $p < 0.05$.; **Critical Value $F\alpha_{0.05, (4)}$ is 9.49

6.2.3. Inference

It can be seen from the above table No-15, shows the chi-square values of given third hypothesis of study has four sub hypotheses relating to women entrepreneur's business performance. Which includes business performance, business challenges, business opportunities and business success.

By applied Chiquare test, it is indicated that all four sub-hypotheses of women entrepreneur's business performance as variables are tested to find the difference of the women entrepreneurs' business performance between rural urban regions in Visakhapatnam. Where, calculated Chi-square values of the four variables less than the critical value, hence all these sub-hypotheses are accepted at 5% level of significance. Therefore, it is observed that business performance, business challenges, business opportunities and business success are subjective factors to differentiating the women entrepreneur's business performance between urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam. Further, it concluded that as per pilot study revealed that women entrepreneur's business performance is different between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam.

7. Conclusion

On the basis of the aforesaid statement of problem, objectives, hypotheses and methodology concerned to the main study titled Impact of Entrepreneurship on Women Empowerment with special reference to Visakhapatnam. An attempt is made to done pilot study out of 450 samples considered 50 samples have been propositioned equally to urban and rural areas of Visakhapatnam region. This pilot study has been classified five sections, which are

- Review the women entrepreneur's socio-economic demographic profile.

- Analysis of Women Entrepreneur's Business capabilities and empowerment.
- Analysis of Women Entrepreneurship on woman empowerment in Urban and Rural Regions.
- Discusses the impact of government policies on women entrepreneurship and empowerment.
- Discusses the problems and prospectus of entrepreneurship on women empowerment.

Major findings

- It is observed that selected four personnel, social and economic profile of women entrepreneurs, those are age, education qualifications, earnings capacity and social status are personnel profiles are subjective factors for decide the performance of entrepreneurship on women empowerment between urban and rural areas in Visakhapatnam.
- As per the study revealed that women entrepreneur's business capabilities and empowerment itself required factors; positive attitude, confidence level, risk taking ability and problem-solving ability are measures the women entrepreneurship and empowerment. This study is also discovered that there is women entrepreneurship performance and empowerment is different between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam.
- It is revealed that women entrepreneur's business performance is different between urban and rural regions in Visakhapatnam based on the following parameters consisting of business performance, business challenges, business opportunities and business success.

Further, this study itself all selected five sections consisting of 20 parameters including demographic profile is got 19 parameters are favourable (95 percent) of this study. It is concluded that selected research topic is possible to arrive the statement of problem, study main objectives and research hypotheses to main study as per my survey data and analysis.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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